

Studies in the Camphor Series. Part I.

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In the present communication a general method of synthesis of cyclic thioketones has been described, by means of which thiocamphor has been synthesised in good yield. Thioborneol in quantity has also been obtained from thiocamphor by reduction.

Attempts have been made from time to time to synthesise thiocamphor in various ways by several investigators who failed to isolate the pure compound, probably owing to the difficulties of its separation from the accompanying bye-products which are formed in quantity with a very small amount of thiocamphor (Wuyts, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 863; Houben and Doescher, *Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 3503; Rimini, *Gazzetta*, 1909, **39**, 11, 196).

The chief disadvantage of the earlier methods of replacing oxygen by sulphur in aldehydes and ketones is that, the resulting thioaldehydes and thioketones in many cases polymerise to form trithio derivatives which have got very little chemical interests (*cf.* Barbaglia and Marquardt, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 1881; Rimini, *loc. cit.*; Fromm and collaborators, *Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 2600; 1890, **23**, 60; Klinger, *ibid.*, 1877, **10**, 1877; Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 25). Fromm (*Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 2090) by passing a current of sulphuretted hydrogen and gaseous hydrochloric acid successively for several times in an alcoholic solution of cyclic ketones like cyclohexanone and cyclopentanone obtained tripolymerised thio derivatives. Mitra (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 471; *ibid.*, 1933, **10**, 71) applied this reaction in the case of β -ketonic esters and obtained better results as he could isolate the nonpolymerised thio derivatives. This last method with sufficient modification (*vide experimental*), can be suitably applied for the preparation of thiocamphor in 50% yield.

It has been possible to synthesise, by the above method two stereoisomeric thio compounds, *racemic* and *laevo* varieties. The *dextro* variety has not yet been obtained. It has been observed that artificial or *r*-camphor as well as *l*-camphor yields *r*-thiocamphor (m. p. 145°) whereas the *d*-camphor when converted to thiocamphor yields the *l*-variety, m. p. 146°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} = -12^\circ$ in 3.5% solution in ethyl acetate

in a tube of length 10 cm. The previous workers have recorded it as $[\alpha]_D^{30} -44^\circ$, in a solution of nearly the same strength. This anomaly cannot be decided till the *d*-variety is isolated. From the above experiments, it can only be assumed at this stage, that so far as optical activity is concerned, the *d*-thiocamphor is an unstable system compared to the *l*-variety, and the *d*-variety has a greater tendency to racemise than the *l*-variety.

The formation of thiocamphor probably takes place through an intermediate unstable hydrochloride and the mechanism can be expressed by the following scheme:—

An unstable hydrochloride of camphor easily decomposable by moisture, has been isolated (Shukoff and Kasatkin, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **41**, 137, 166), which to some extent supports this view. That thiocamphor cannot be prepared by means of sulphuretted hydrogen in presence of a moderate dehydrating agent like anhydrous sodium sulphate furnishes additional support to this view. As regards the constitution of camphor hydrochloride also, there are different views, for example, some describe it as a molecular compound $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{OHCl}$,

others as an oxonium compound $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14} \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_2 \\ | \\ \text{C}:\text{O} \begin{array}{l} \text{H} \\ \text{Cl} \end{array} \end{array} \right.$ while others

ascribe to it, the constitutional formula described above (II). From the constitutional formulæ of well-known additive compounds of ketones, *e.g.*, cyanhydrin, phosphoric acid derivatives, etc., the constitutional formula of this hydrochloride should be represented as in (II).

Regarding the constitution of thiocamphor, its direct synthesis from camphor shows that it is a thioketone formed simply by the

replacement of oxygen by means of sulphur. It forms phenylhydrazones, semicarbazone and oxime, which are identical with those of camphor as supported by their unchanged mixed melting points and analytical data. The behaviour of thioketones is thus analogous to that of ketones.

The slight difference between thiocamphor, thioborneol and dibornyl disulphide with respect to analytical data, does not prove conclusively, whether the substance isolated is pure thiocamphor. But the above reactions and molecular weight data and nearly the quantitative formation of semicarbazone prove conclusively that it is pure thiocamphor and not a disulphide. That it cannot form a yellow lead salt nor can it decolourise iodine solution prove that it does not contain thioborneol as an impurity.

Thioborneol has been prepared from thiocamphor by reduction with zinc and hydrochloric acid. The previous workers Wuyts, Rimini, etc. (*loc. cit.*) obtained thioborneol by decomposing the lead salt with acetic acid during which, evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen takes place and an impure substance is obtained whose m. p. is described by some workers as 50° and by others as 62-65°, whereas the m. p. observed by the present author is 120°. The above operation also diminishes the yield of thioborneol to a marked degree. A very small quantity of an oily liquid accompanies thioborneol and this lowers the m. p. to a considerable extent. Thioborneol forms dibornyl disulphide (A, m. p. 198°) by treatment with iodine in alcoholic solution.

(A)

Here also, the m. p. is found to be much higher than that described by the earlier workers (*cf.* Houben and Doescher, *loc. cit.*, m. p. 178°).

The above facts show that thiocamphor, thioborneol and their derivatives in the pure state were not known and the little study that has been made in this line also abounds in errors.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of thiocamphor.—Camphor (30 g.) in absolute alcohol (150 c. c.) was cooled to 0° and dry HCl gas and H₂S were passed

simultaneously for 5-6 hours. The solution changed from yellow, orange to deep red. The alcoholic solution was then treated with ice-cold water (25 c.c.) and the red precipitate was immediately filtered, as thiocamphor in the moist state is easily oxidisable. The precipitate was washed with dilute alcohol (1:1), then with a dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate and finally washed several times with water. The filtrate on further dilution gave more of the precipitate and this fractional precipitation is necessary, for, if camphor is precipitated along with thiocamphor it is very difficult to separate the two. The precipitate was then dissolved in benzene, the solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and benzene evaporated, when octahedral crystals separate from the concentrated solution, m. p. 145°, yield 15-16 g. The substance smells like camphor with a slightly sulphurous smell. It sublimes like camphor, is sparingly soluble in water and is readily soluble in common organic solvents. It is optically inactive. Like camphor it is acted upon by a chloroform solution of bromine and with sulphuric acid in presence of acetic anhydride. *l*-Camphor when similarly converted to thiocamphor gives the same racemic compound. [Found: C, 71.12; H, 9.6; S, 19.09. M. W. in benzene (cryoscopic), 167, 165. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}S$: C, 71.43; H, 9.52; S, 19.05 per cent. M. W., 168].

On subjecting *d*-camphor to the above treatment *l*-thiocamphor was obtained, m. p. 146°; $[\alpha]_D^{30} -12^\circ$, in a 3.5% ethyl acetate solution observed in a tube of length 10 cm. (Found: C, 71.18; H, 9.7; S, 19.1. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}S$: C, 71.43; H, 9.52; S, 19.05 per cent).

The phenylhydrazone—Thiocamphor (4 g.) was heated with phenylhydrazine (4 g.) on the water-bath till sulphuretted hydrogen was no longer evolved. The resulting product was dissolved in ether and the ethereal solution washed with a dilute solution of hydrochloric acid, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled under reduced pressure, yield 3 g. It boils at 190°/10 mm. and at 230° (decomp.) under atmospheric pressure. It is identical with camphor-phenylhydrazone (*cf.* Balbiano, *Gazzetta*, 1885, 15, 246; Wuyts, *loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 78.68; H, 9.22; M. W., 244.4. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{22}N_2$: C, 79.34; H, 9.1 per cent. M. W., 242).

The *oxime* was prepared as usual by refluxing for 2 hours an alcoholic solution of thiocamphor (5 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (5 g.) and sodium acetate (7.5 g.). It was crystallised from alcohol

as needle-shaped crystals, m. p. 118-19° (mixed m. p. with camphor oxime). (Found: N, 8·31. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{17}ON$: N, 8·38 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol as needle-shaped crystals, m. p. 237° (mixed m. p. with camphor semicarbazone). (Found: N, 20·12. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{19}ON_3$: N, 20·09 per cent).

Reduction of thiocamphor: Preparation of thioborneol.—This substance has been prepared by Wuyts, Rimini and others (*loc. cit.*), but the experimental details are not described. The action of zinc and acetic acid and also that of zinc and hydrochloric acid were tried, but in both cases, sulphuretted hydrogen was evolved during reduction, resulting in the formation of sulphur compounds of indefinite composition along with thioborneol. To the ice-cooled solution of thiocamphor (5 g.), in alcohol (25 c. c.), containing granulated zinc, an equal volume of a saturated solution of alcoholic hydrochloric acid was added and the solution kept overnight when the red colour was practically discharged. The reaction was allowed to take place finally for sometime at the ordinary temperature. Thioborneol was precipitated from the solution by means of ice-cold water and the product extracted with ether, dehydrated, and the ether evaporated. The solid was then dissolved in alcohol and treated with alcoholic solution of lead acetate when the insoluble lead salt of thioborneol separated out. The lead salt was suspended in alcohol and the lead removed as PbS. The thioborneol was precipitated from the alcoholic solution with water and extracted with ether, the ether distilled off, when a white solid with a small quantity of an oil separated out. On removing the oil on a porous plate the solid was crystallised as needles from ether, alcohol or petroleum ether, m. p. 120° (m. p. 61-62°, *cf.* Wuyts, *loc. cit.*). This also has camphoric smell sweeter than that of thiocamphor. It is soluble in common organic solvents. [Found: C, 70·74; H, 10·72; S, 18·81; M. W. in benzene (cryoscopic) 172·2. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{17}S$: C, 70·59; H, 10·59; S, 18·82 per cent. M. W., 170]. The yellow lead salt is fairly soluble in ether and can be crystallised from it as minute needles. [Found: S, 11·58. $Pb(C_{10}H_{17}S)_2$ requires S, 11·74 per cent].

Conversion of thioborneol to dibornyl disulphide.—Alcoholic solution of thioborneol (2 g.) was treated with an alcoholic solution of iodine till the brown colour became persistent and the excess of iodine was removed after 2 hours with sodium thiosulphate solution. The disulphide was precipitated by the addition of water and crystallised

from alcohol as needles, m. p. 198°, yield 1.8 g. It has slight camphoric smell. It is much less soluble than either thiocamphor or thioborneol. It is less sublimable than thiocamphor. [Found: C, 70.6; H, 10.3; S, 18.81; M. W. in benzene (cryoscopic), 335.6. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{34}S_2$: C, 71.01; H, 10.06; S, 18.93 per cent. M. W., 338]

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The Formation of Amides from Nitriles by the Action of Hydrogen Peroxide.

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In a recent paper Murray and Cloke (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2749) report the advantage of using a solvent such as methanol, ethanol or acetone in the Radziszewski reaction. The same conclusion was reached by us a few years ago during the course of a fairly detailed study of the optimum conditions for this reaction. Because of the inaccessibility of these data, it is thought desirable to briefly summarise them here.

In general, the hydrogen peroxide was added to a weighed portion of the nitrile and sufficient 95% ethanol added to bring the nitrile into solution. Sufficient 6N-sodium hydroxide was added to make the solution alkaline to litmus after which it was kept at 60° for 4 hours. If necessary, more sodium hydroxide was added during the course of the reaction to keep the mixture alkaline. The mixture was then cooled, neutralised with sulphuric acid, evaporated to dryness and either extracted with chloroform or crystallised from water. The amides were finally purified to constant melting point. In a few cases no ethanol was used but the nitrile was stirred with the hydrogen peroxide. The best conditions as determined by from two to eight experiments for each nitrile, using 3, 6, 12 and 30% hydrogen peroxide, are given in the following table.